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**RAILWAY TRACK SUPPORT CONDITION
ASSESSMENT - PRELIMINARY VALIDATION
TESTS USING A MULTIBODY SIMULATION
SOFTWARE**

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SUMMARY

Assessing railway track support conditions is an important activity for railway managers around the world. In this context, an alternative and novel methodology to evaluate railway track support conditions is now under development. This methodology is based on modal analysis of the multi-element system composed by a railway infrastructure and an instrumented railway vehicle moving over it. It belongs to the group of vibration-based structural damage identification methods and is focused on observing the characteristic frequencies of this multi-element system, which can be related with changes in the physical properties of the railway infrastructure under analysis. An important feature of the proposed methodology is that it should enable the collection of information regarding the conditions of a railway infrastructure's subgrade, an element that is often overlooked during monitoring operations. By performing this assessment of a railway infrastructure over its length, and over time by comparing different rides over the same railway stretch, important information can be gathered regarding the support conditions of the track.

An important aspect of this methodology that must be validated is the suitability of the underlying theoretical model to adequately describe reality and its usefulness in interpreting the data acquired with an instrumented vehicle. More specifically, the topic of characterizing track support conditions of a railway infrastructure through its natural frequencies is something that must still be validated. Numerical simulations tests using the multibody simulation software Simpack are currently being performed to assess this topic. This paper describes the preliminary simulations performed in this context, including a description of the Simpack model used. The obtained results support the selection of the proposed theoretical model and represent an important step in the validation of the methodology.

Keywords

Track monitoring, Track support conditions, Modal analysis, Vibration-based structural damage identification methods, Vehicle-based inspection, Signal processing

INTRODUCTION

The railway sector always had an important role in multiple aspects of society, including on social and economic issues. Nowadays, most modern and developing countries still spend considerable resources in creating, maintaining and modernizing railway infrastructures and vehicles. As part of these overall efforts, the assessment of railway track support conditions is an important task because it has a direct impact on railway maintenance management, operational safety, and general reliability and availability of this service.

One of the more established parameters for the assessment of railway track support conditions is vertical track stiffness, which is defined as the ratio between the vertical load applied on the rail and the maximum vertical displacement of the track (Esveld, 2001). This parameter can thus be used to monitor the capacity of a railway track to reliably support its respective railway traffic (Le Pen et al, 2016). There are other parameters that can also be used to assess specific aspects of track support conditions, such as monitoring track geometry or track irregularities and defects. While relevant and extensively used in railway monitoring operations, all of these parameters also have some limitations that have been reported over the years (Innotrack, 2008; Rivas, 2013; Wang et al, 2016). For example, vehicle-based monitoring methods based on these parameters are usually more focused on the conditions of the track superstructure (Esveld, 2001; Berggren, 2009). This means that the track substructure (Figure 1), that includes the track subgrade layers, remains unchecked due to the nature of what these parameters can adequately assess with these methods (Innotrack, 2008; Wang et al, 2016). This is an important issue since subgrade condition represents one of the main aspects that influences track dynamic response and track support conditions of a railway infrastructure (Selig and Li, 1994; Esveld, 2001; Auersch, 2005; Berggren, 2009).

Figure 1: Schematic representation of a ballasted railway track infrastructure.

An alternative and novel methodology to evaluate railway track support conditions is now under development in the context of a research study. This methodology is based on modal analysis of the characteristic frequencies of the multi-element system composed by an instrumented

railway vehicle and a railway infrastructure. An important feature of the proposed methodology is that it should be able to assess the conditions of the subgrade of a railway infrastructure under evaluation (Doebeling et al, 1998). This is the case because both the railway superstructure and the substructure are dynamically excited by the moving vehicle, thus their dynamic response can be monitored and used to gather data on their respective conditions (Esveld, 2001; Innotrack, 2008; Berggren, 2009; Wang et al, 2016). More specifically, information related with track stiffness should be obtainable by monitoring these characteristics frequencies, since modal stiffness is a parameter that is highly influenced by the appearance of damage in a structure (Doebeling et al, 1998; Kong and Cai, 2017). These two types of stiffness concepts cannot be compared directly, because they have different definitions, but they are related with each other (Esveld, 2001). Thus, information regarding infrastructure support conditions can be extracted from these frequencies, especially data on subgrade condition due to its major influence on track dynamic response. This is particularly relevant because track subgrade represents one of the main contributors to overall track support conditions, (Selig and Li, 1994; Esveld, 2001; Berggren, 2009; Wang et al, 2016), but is often overlooked in favour of the more accessible superstructure elements.

To interpret the acquired railway related data, this methodology proposes the use of a lumped-elements type model (Figure 2). The current version of the proposed methodology uses a two Degree-of-Freedom (2-DoF) model to describe the vehicle, per axle, and the modal properties of the railway infrastructure. This model consists of two spring-mass sub-systems in series. The mass elements represent the unsprung mass of one vehicle axle plus the modal mass of the infrastructure that is being dynamically excited by the moving vehicle (m_1), and the vehicle's sprung mass section that is supported by the axle (m_2). These two mass elements are linked by the vehicle's suspension system (k_2). The last element is a spring representing the infrastructure modal stiffness (k_1), combining the superstructure and the substructure.

Figure 2: 2-DoF model used in the current version of the methodology.

The output of this model are two characteristic frequencies (ω_1 and ω_2), that are related with these four modal parameters (Maia and Silva, 1997). Frequency ω_2 is mainly related with the vehicle's modal characteristics and can be attributed to the vertical oscillatory motion of the vehicle's sprung mass, with typical values between 1 and 5 Hz (Zhai, 2020). On the other hand, frequency ω_1 is mainly influenced by the modal parameters of the railway infrastructure elements, thus represents the main natural frequency of interest for the proposed methodology. A preliminary test on this methodology has already been implemented with experimental data. This test was used to assess the developed data processing tools, and to perform a preliminary assessment on the overall concept (Morais et al, 2021).

Considering the potential of vehicle-based solutions to provide extensive assessments on a continuous mechanical system such as a railway line, it is expected that the monitored characteristic frequencies can create perceivable patterns or curves if the resulting spectrums are represented in the time-frequency domain (Auersch, 2005; Zhai, 2020). These patterns can represent another source of relevant information on this combined mechanical system by studying their shapes and behaviour, and not just monitor the frequency values of interest (Salvador et al, 2016; Vinberg et al, 2018).

At this stage, an important aspect of this methodology that needs to be validated is the assessment of track support conditions of a railway infrastructure section through its natural frequencies. More specifically, the present research intends to prove that it is possible to observe a dominant resonance frequency related with the railway infrastructure under assessment, and that this frequency is adequate to provide useful information on the track's support conditions. This hypothesis represents one of the cornerstones of this methodology, due to the current intent of trying to assess track support conditions of a railway infrastructure based on monitoring only one resonance frequency (ω_1) (i.e., a dominant resonance frequency). The simulations described in the paper were performed as part of the efforts to assess and validate this topic. Thus, the following hypothesis was assessed here:

- **H1:** a single dominant resonance frequency related with the dynamic response of an entire railway infrastructure section exists and is observable in data collected with an instrumented vehicle moving over a railway track.

The ideal situation for H1 would be to observe this dominant resonance frequency at the car level of the vehicle, as opposed to in the axles or the bogies. This scenario would represent a more beneficial situation where the natural filtering effect of the suspensions could be used to provide cleaner data in terms of mechanical noise, thus resulting in clearer frequency spectrums from the methodology (Zhai, 2020).

1. SIMPACK MODEL DESCRIPTION

To assess the validity of the previous hypothesis, a Simpack model containing a railway vehicle and railway infrastructure elements was assembled. The railway vehicle model represented a typical passenger carriage with two bogies. It included all the relevant elements associated with its functional aspects, namely: springs and dampers for the two levels of suspension systems (i.e., lower or primary suspension and upper or secondary suspension), and mass elements to represent both the sprung and unsprung masses of the vehicle. As for the railway infrastructure, it was described by specific elements representing the two rails and one moving sleeper plus two relatively short cylinders stacked on top of each other (Figure 3). These cylinders were designed to represent different layers of the infrastructure, namely a ballast layer and a subgrade layer. The dimensions of the layered infrastructure elements were determined through an iterative process. The selection was done by comparing the local natural frequencies values of each element, calculated by Simpack, with the typical frequency ranges for the respective layer of a railway infrastructures (De Man, 2002; Kouroussis et al, 2015; Salvador et al, 2016). These infrastructure elements were placed only below the frontal axle of the vehicle to reduce computational effort. During model development, a model with infrastructure elements below each axle was tested and the obtained results were equivalent to the final situation in terms of the obtained frequency spectrums.

Figure 3: Sub-section of the Simpack model used, containing the frontal bogie of the vehicle and the model elements representing the railway infrastructure.

Coupled with the sleeper element and the two layered elements of the infrastructure, this model contained spring-damper elements to simulate the equivalent vertical stiffness behaviour from each part. The discretization of the infrastructure into multiple elements, specifically the layered components (i.e., ballast and subgrade), was done to allow for an adequate assessment of H1. That is, if the infrastructure was described by only a single element, the scenario described in hypothesis H1 would be naturally verified because of the bias created by the model's structure

(i.e., one element only provides one natural frequency). This would prevent the proper assessment of H1. Thus, the layered parts of the railway infrastructure were described by these two elements, to more adequately represent the main contributors to the natural frequencies of interest (Selig and Li, 1994; Esveld, 2001).

Table 1 and Table 2 present the values used for the main modal parameters of the tested model. The parameter values for the vehicle elements are in accordance with typical values used on consulted bibliography (Milne et al., 2019; Zhai, 2020), as are the density values used to calculate the mass for each element of the infrastructure and the equivalent stiffness values used on their respective spring elements (Milne et al., 2019).

Table 1: Main parameters used in the tested Simpack vehicle model.

Vehicle Parameters	Value
Car body mass	35000 kg
Bogie mass	2615 kg
Axle mass	1200 kg
Primary suspension stiffness	1.82 kN/mm
Secondary suspension stiffness	6.43 kN/mm
Primary suspension damping	42000 Ns/m
Secondary suspension damping	25000 Ns/m

Table 2: Main parameters used in the tested Simpack infrastructure model.

Infrastructure Parameters	Value
Subgrade layer mass	13770 kg
Ballast layer mass	3098 kg
Sleeper mass	330 kg
Layered elements diameter	3 m
Subgrade layer height	1 m
Ballast layer height	0.3 m
Sleeper spacing	0.5 m
Subgrade layer spring element stiffness	150 kN/mm
Ballast layer spring element stiffness	450 kN/mm
Sleeper spring element stiffness	225 kN/mm
Layered elements damping	37600 Ns/m

Since the main objectives of these simulations required a scenario with varying track support conditions, the modal stiffness values of the infrastructure elements were super-imposed with track stiffness variation profiles. These profiles were designed to create situations where significantly different resonance frequency values could be perceived, and less focused on representing any specific real scenario.

Finally, a relatively simple vehicle running speed profile was established to create a simulation where the system's frequencies that are dependent on the vehicle's speed could be distinguished from the system's structural frequencies (Esveld, 2001). The characteristic frequencies of a linear mechanical system are independent of the excitation signal's characteristics used to assess them (Doebeling et al, 1998). In this context, this means that the system's natural frequencies are independent of the vehicle's running speed. Thus, the frequencies that depend on vehicle running speed can be discarded during data processing, enabling the user to focus on the natural frequencies of interest. This task of distinguishing between these two types of frequencies is made easier if the collected frequency spectrums are represented in the time-frequency domain, such as in a spectrogram.

This model also had a relatively simple track cartographic profile, in terms of slopes and curves, just to demonstrate that these parameters do not interfere with the frequencies of interest. The track implemented in this model had two slope changes and two moderate curves. The overall track length for the model was 2000 m.

Figure 4: Simpack model of a railway vehicle with bogies and a railway track.

The simulations were conducted using a sampling frequency of 1000 Hz, and a run-time of 160 s. The model had a virtual accelerometer placed in the frontal vehicle axle, another on the frontal bogie, and a third on the vehicle's car directly above the frontal axle, to monitor the dynamic response from the infrastructure elements directly below. These monitoring spots were selected to provide the acceleration data to be used to assess the previous hypothesis, including to assess where the dominant natural frequency described in H1 can be observed.

2. RESULTS

This section presents the data obtained from the tested model, and all the relevant results acquired from it. Frequency results from the bogie sensor will not be shown because they are very similar in aspect to the car related results. All data will be presented in the space domain, instead of the time domain, since this representation is typically more suitable when monitoring railway lines with a vehicle-based solution (Berggren, 2009; Zhai, 2020). Figure 5 presents the raw data obtained for this simulation. As expected, the acceleration data from the axle sensor has significantly higher amplitude values than the data from the other two sensors (Zhai, 2020), due to the filtering feature provided by the suspension systems of the vehicle. This difference is also reflected in the respective frequency spectrums. The bumps in the acceleration data in the bogie and car sensors, at the 200 m and 1150 m marks, correspond to the observable effects of the two slopes in the cartographic profile of this model's track.

Figure 5: Raw data from the simulation (acceleration data and vehicle running speed).

Then Figure 6 presents the obtained spectrograms from the axle (spectrogram A) and the car (spectrogram C) acceleration data, and the vertical track stiffness profiles used on the spring elements associated with the two layered elements of the infrastructure. Both spectrograms present mostly the same observable frequency curves, except for two specific main differences. One difference is that spectrogram A does not present any significant frequency content below 5 Hz, while spectrogram C presents frequency curves in this area that correspond to natural frequencies of the car (Zhai, 2020). These frequencies do not appear in the axle sensor, again due to the presence of the filtering effect from the suspension system. The other relevant difference is that some of the frequency content that appears on spectrogram A is significantly mitigated in spectrogram C, especially the content around the 80 to 90 Hz range.

Figure 6: Obtained spectrograms and applied track stiffness profiles from the simulation.

The next step in the methodology's implementation process is to extract the frequency content of interest from the spectrograms, by discarding the irrelevant frequency curves. In this context, an important distinction to be made is between the frequencies that depend on the vehicle's running speed (F_{ds}) from those that are independent from it (F_{is}). As previously explained, the characteristic frequencies of this combined mechanical system, which include the frequencies of interest to the methodology, are not dependant on the vehicle's speed. Thus, frequencies that can be correlated with the vehicle's speed curve, which is represented in Figure 5, can be discarded. In these spectrograms there is only one F_{ds} curve, which corresponds to the frequency created by the interaction of the vehicle's wheels with the spacing of the sleepers. Additionally, the F_{is} curves present in Spectrogram C below the 5 Hz mark can also be discarded because these correspond to natural frequencies of the car (Zhai, 2020).

Finally, the three observable F_{is} curves that remain, identified in Figure 6, had to be analysed. Due to the damping effect of the suspension system, the F_{is} curve with the higher frequency values that is observable in spectrogram A is barely visible in spectrogram C. But the other two frequency curves appear in both spectrograms. The Simpack tool that calculates and represents the kinematics of each natural frequency present on a simulated model, using its initial conditions, states that these frequencies correspond to three different modes of vibration from the infrastructure elements coupled with the unsprung mass of the vehicle (i.e., the frontal axle).

According to this tool, these two groups of elements form a sub-system that is dynamically excited during the simulation, thus presenting natural frequencies that can be associated with the railway infrastructure. Table 3 presents the values given by Simpack for these three natural frequencies, which match the values presented in both spectrograms in the initial conditions, along with a brief description on their kinematic behaviour (i.e., mode shapes) based on the three main elements of this sub-system (wheelset [W], ballast layer [B] and subgrade layer [S]).

Table 3: Infrastructure related vibration modes from the tested Simpack model.

Natural Frequency description	Kinematics (W,B,S)	Frequency value
Full body sub-system oscillation (1 st mode)	↑↑↑ ↓↓↓	14.11 Hz
Wheelset + Ballast in opposition to Subgrade oscillation (2 nd mode)	↑↑↓ ↓↓↑	47.47 Hz
Ballast in opposition to Subgrade + Wheelset oscillation (3 rd mode)	↑↓↑ ↓↓↓	85.28 Hz

These three curves resemble the vertical track stiffness profiles applied to the layered infrastructure elements, which supports the statement that these natural frequency curves are related with them. More specifically, the first mode appears to be heavily influenced by the subgrade track stiffness profile, which agrees with the mode shape description that this vibration mode corresponds to the oscillation of the entire mass of the infrastructure plus the frontal axle of the vehicle over the spring that connects the infrastructure to the world (i.e., the subgrade spring element). The second mode's curve resembles the ballast track stiffness profile, which also agrees with the shape mode's description where it is reasonable that the ballast spring element should be the main influencer. The third mode's curve seems to be a combination of influences from the two track stiffness profiles, which again also agrees with the respective shape mode description. Considering the behaviour of these three natural frequencies, the first mode of vibration described in Table 3 appears to correspond to the intended behaviour of the dominant resonance frequency entailed in hypothesis H1. This natural frequency presents the highest amplitude value from these modes and is highly sensitive to the track stiffness of the subgrade layer. Thus, it represents the more appropriate mode shape to describe the expected behaviour of a real railway infrastructure. While the soil layers of a real railway infrastructure can present individual natural frequencies (Selig and Waters, 1994; Esveld, 2001), in the author's opinion, the more observable behaviour from the point of view of a railway vehicle should be the full body oscillation of the entire section of the infrastructure that is being excited by the moving vehicle. The assessment and validation of this topic is one of the main tasks of this ongoing research since it is a vital aspect of the proposed methodology. The assessment of H1 in this simulated environment represents one of the steps in this process. Thus, from the previous results, hypothesis H1 is validated for this model by selecting the first vibration mode previously described as the dominant resonance frequency of interest.

3. CONCLUSIONS

An alternative and novel methodology to assess railway track support conditions based on modal analysis of the characteristic frequencies of a multi-element system, composed by a railway infrastructure and an instrumented railway vehicle moving over it, is under development as part of an ongoing research. The proposed methodology is integrated in the group of vibration-based structural damage identification methods. This methodology should be able to provide information on the track support conditions of a railway infrastructure, including the assessment of subgrade conditions, by providing tools to analyse and interpret the natural frequencies of this part of a railway track.

This paper presents a brief description on the ongoing research on this newly proposed methodology, followed by a description of one representative numerical simulation test performed in this context. The intent of this simulation, performed with Simpack, was to assess the validity of one hypothesis regarding the capability of the proposed methodology, and its associated tools, to adequately provide useful results on track support conditions. Namely, the hypothesis was whether a dominant resonance frequency from a railway infrastructure could be identified and be reliably observable from the point of view of a moving instrumented railway vehicle.

This hypothesis was validated in the tested model conditions. But this conclusion can be potentially extrapolated into a more general validation in simulated environments due to the characteristics of the model used. For instance, if the infrastructure sub-model had additional layers beyond the two used, the tested hypothesis would still be valid because of the relevant linear behaviour of the model (Maia and Silva, 1997). This result represents an important step in the overall validation process of the proposed methodology, but there is still the need to validate this hypothesis with experimental data. If future validations steps on this methodology also prove to be successful, this would represent an alternative method to assess railway infrastructures with instrumented vehicles, focused on track support conditions and some aspects of subgrade structural health.

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